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ASSESSMENT OF THE DEGREE OF PRESERVATION OF CORONARY RESERVES IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH MITRAL STENOSIS.....11
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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE CONDITION OF WOMEN DURING CESAREAN SECTION UNDER SPINAL ANESTHESIA AND MEDICAL SEDATION.....16
3. **Khudoyberdieva Gulrukh Sobirovna, Matlubov Mansur Muratovich**
SEDATION AND PSYCHO-EMOTIONAL STATUS OF WOMEN IN REGIONAL ANESTHESIA FOR CAESAREAN SECTION. CURRENT STATE OF THE PROBLEM.....24
4. **Sharipov Isroil Latipovich**
HEMODYNAMIC GRADATIONS DURING COMBINED USAGE OF EXTRACORPORAL DETOXIFICATION METHODS IN CHILDREN WITH RENAL FAILURE.....31
5. **Pardaev Shukur Kuylievich, Sharipov Isroil Latipovich**
APPLICATION OF CENTRAL NEURAXIAL ANESTHESIA IN THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF LUMBAR-SACRAL DISC HERNIATIONS.....38
6. **Yusupov Jasur Tolibovich, Matlubov Mansur Muratovich**
ENHANCING INTENSIVE CARE FOR PATIENTS FOLLOWING CORONARY ARTERY BYPASS GRAFTING (LITERATURE REVIEW).....44

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7. **Ahmedova Aziza Tayirovna, Rasulova Feruza Golibovna**
ASSESSMENT OF PERINATAL COMPLICATIONS RISK USING REMOTE CARDIOTOCOGRAPHY MONITORING.....52
8. **Agababyan Larisa Rubenovna, Usmankulova Habiba Mizrobjonovna**
NEW TREATMENT OPPORTUNITIES FOR POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME.....59
9. **Nasirova Zebiniso Azizovna**
APPROACHES TO THE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF ANEMIA IN HEAVY MENSTRUAL BLEEDING.....66
10. **Zakirova Nodira Islomovna, Yuldasheva Farangiz Ismatilloevna**
CORRECTION AND TACTICS OF PREGNANCY ADMINISTRATION IN CASE OF VIOLATIONS OF THE VAGINAL ECOSYSTEM.....76

INFECTIOUS DISEASES

11. **Orzikulov Azam Orzikulovich, Haydarov Akbar Haydarovich**
ANTIVIRAL THERAPY IN VIRAL HEPATITIS “C” DISEASE EFFICIENCY (A CASE FROM PRACTICE).....80
12. **Oslanov Absamat Abdurakhimovich, Soibnazarov Orzukul Ernazarovich**
COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CONTRIBUTION OF THE VIRAL LOAD TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF LIVER FIBROSIS IN CHRONIC HEPATITIS «B» (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE SAMARKAND REGION).....86
13. **Kadirov Zhonibek Fayzullayevich, Rizaev Jasur Alimdjanovich, Ziyadullaev Shukhrat Khudayberdiyevich**
MOLECULAR MECHANISMS OF IMMUNOLOGICAL ACTIVATION IN HIV INFECTION.....92

ENDOCRINOLOGY

14. **Egamova Malika Tursunovna, Rasulov Jamshedjon Shavkatovich**
EFFICACY OF FOLK REMEDIES IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS AT RISK OF STROKE.....106
15. **Egamova Malika Tursunovna, Ergashev Asadullo Ubaydullo o'g'li**
THE IMPORTANCE OF BLOOD RHEOLOGY IN DIABETES IN THE ORIGIN OF ISCHEMIC STROKE AND THE EFFECT OF HIRUDOTHERAPY ON BLOOD RHEOLOGY.....111
16. **Fozilova Umida Kamalovna, Khabibova Nazira Nasulloevna.**
THE ROLE OF GLYCEMIC CONTROL IN PREVENTING DENTAL COMPLICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES(REVIEW ARTICLE).....116
17. **Saidova Shakhnoza Aripovna, Yakubov Abdusalol Vahobovich, Pulatova Durдона Baxadirovna**
THE EFFECT OF GLP-1 RECEPTOR AGONISM ON DIVERSE ASPECTS OF THE CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES AND OBESITY.....122

MORPHOLOGY

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE GALLBLADDER WALL IN EXPERIMENTAL CALCULOUS CHOLECYSTITIS IN LABORATORY ANIMALS.....128
19. **M.A. Abdullayeva, O.O. Zaripova.**
DETERMINATION OF THE ACCUMULATION LEVEL OF ARTIFICIAL FOOD COLORANTS E 171 AND E 173 IN THE BRAIN.....135
20. **Mamataliyev Abdumalik Rasulovich**
ANATOMICAL AND TOPOGRAPHICAL STRUCTURE OF THE EXTRAHEPATIC BILE DUCT IN EXPERIMENTAL ANIMALS.....140
21. **Ismailov Jasur Mardonovich**
ABOUT BRONCHIECTASIS AS A TYPE OF CHRONIC NONSPECIFIC LUNG DISEASE.....144
22. **Ismailov Jasur Mardonovich, Norjigitov Azamat Musokulovich**
MORPHOLOGY AND MORPHOMETRIC INDICATORS OF BRONCHI AND LUNG TISSUES IN CHILDREN WITH BRONCHIECTASIS.....150
23. **Juraev Kamoliddin Danabaevich, Islamov Shavkat Erjigitovich**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE THYMUS IN NEWBORNS IN THE LATE NEONATAL PERIOD.....158
24. **Rakhimova Gulnoz Shamsievna, Teshayev Shuxrat Jumayevich.**
ASSESSMENT OF MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE TESTES ON THE FIRST DAY AFTER ACUTE TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY.....168

NEUROLOGY AND NEUROSURGERY

25. **Ruzmetova Saodat Umarjonovna**
FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF EARLY POSTNATAL HEALTH IN CHILDREN WHO HAVE SUFFERED PERINATAL CNS DAMAGE.....173
26. **Khakimova Sakhiba Ziyadullaevna, Gaffarova Parvina Abdurafikovna, Abruev Khudoerkhon Oybekovich**
CLINICAL FEATURES OF PARKINSON'S DISEASE IN THYROID HOMEOSTASIS DISRUPTION.....178

27. **Adambaev Zufar Ibragimovich, Kilichev Ibodullo Abdullayevich, Samiyev Asliddin Sayitovich, Khudoyberganov Nurmamat Yusupovich, Pazilova Aida Sultanovna**
CORRECTION OF COGNITIVE IMPAIRMENTS IN CHRONIC CEREBRAL ISCHEMIA IN OUTPATIENT SETTINGS.....185
28. **Khakimova Sohiba Ziyadulloevna, Nurboeva Iroda Samariddin Qizi**
PARKINSON'S DISEASE.....192
29. **Khamdamova Bakhora Komiljonovna, Kodirov Umid Arzikulovich, Muhammadiyeva Dilafruz Po'lot qizi**
INNOVATIVE METHODS OF THERAPY FOR NEUROVASCULAR DISORDERS IN LUMBAR SPINE DORSOPATHIES.....202
30. **Gaffarova Parvina Abdurafikovna, Khakimova Sakhiba Ziyadulloevna**
DANCE MOVEMENT REHABILITATION TO REDUCE COMPLICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH EARLY-ONSET PARKINSON'S DISEASE.....209
31. **Kodirov Umid Arzikulovich, Khakimova Sohiba Ziyadulloevna, Zoxidjonova Shahnoza Zoxidjonovna**
FEATURES OF PSYCHOPATHOLOGICAL AND AUTONOMIC DISORDERS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC PAIN SYNDROME WITH RADICULOPATHIES.....216
32. **Ergasheva Munisa Yakubovna.**
IMPROVING MEASURES FOR REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES DUE TO NERVOUS SYSTEM DISEASES.....222
33. **Raimova Malika Mukhamedjanovna, Yodgarova Umida Gaybulloyevna**
IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS BY STUDYING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RESTLESS LEGS SYNDROME AND HYPOTHYROIDISM.....229

UROLOGY

34. **Allazov Iskandar Salax Ugli, Allazov Salax Allazovich, Ablyatifov Aziz Baxtiyarovich**
OUTPATIENT UROLOGICAL-POLICLINICAL CARE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....235
35. **Allazov Salakh Allazovich, Allazov Iskandar Salakh Ogli, Ergashev Arslonbek Shuxratjon Ogli**
MEDICAL-SOCIAL AND ORGANIZATIONAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF UROLOGICAL DISEASES. LITERATURE REVIEW.....242
36. **Allazov Salakh Allazovich, Batirov Bekhzod Amindjanovich.**
DISTRIBUTION OF UROLOGICAL DISEASES AND METHODS FOR THEIR DETECTION PHARMACOLOGY AND TRADITIONAL MEDICINE.....247
37. **Mirrakhimova Maktuba Habibullaevna, Nishanbaeva Nilufar Yunusjanovna**
FILAGGRIN DEFECT IN ATOPIC DERMATITIS AND MODERN METHODS OF CORRECTION.....256
38. **Egamova Malika Tursunovna, Rasulov Jamshedjon Shavkatovich.**
HIRUDOTHERAPY, THE EFFECT OF VARIOUS TREATMENT METHODS.....262

PEDIATRICS AND PEDIATRIC SURGERY

39. **Abdullaev Zafar Bobirovich, Agzamkhodjaev Saidanvar Talatovich**
ANTENATAL DIAGNOSTICS OF BLADDER EXTROPHY: CONTEMPORARY POSSIBILITIES AND PROSPECTS.....267
40. **Rakhimova Durdona Zhurakulovna**
HYGIENIC ASSESSMENT OF ACTUAL NUTRITION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN.....274

41. **Ganiev Abdurashid Ganievich, Sanakulov Abdulatif Burkhanovich**
ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF ATOPIC DERMATITIS ON THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF THE FAMILY OF A SICK CHILD.....284
42. **Naimushina Elena Serafimovna, Kilina Alla Vladimirovna, Chervinskih Tatyana Anatolyevna**
GENDER-SPECIFIC CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF OBESITY IN ADOLESCENTS.....293
43. **Nuritdinova Gavhar Taipovna, Inakova Barno Bahodirovna, Abduvahobova Gulmira, Arzibekova Umida Abdukodirovna.**
DELAYED NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT IN NEWBORNS WITH MODERATE AND SEVERE ASPHYXIA.....299
44. **Ollabergenov Odilbek, Baratov Feruz**
MINIMALLY INVASIVE INTERVENTIONS IN ACUTE PLEURAL EMPYEMA IN CHILDREN.....305

ONCOLOGY

45. **Ulmasov Firdavs Gayratovich, Esankulova Bustonoy Sobirovna.**
THE ROLE OF VASCULAR ENDOTHELIAL GROWTH FACTOR (VEGF) IN OVARIAN CANCER WITH PERITONEAL CARCINOMATOSIS IN STAGES III AND IV.....311
46. **Kahharov Alisher, Khodjayeva Nozima**
THE IMPACT OF FERTILITY PRESERVATION PROGRAMS ON THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF WOMEN WITH ONCOLOGICAL DISEASES.....318
47. **Zaripova Parvina Ilkhomovna, Yorov Lutfillo Shukurulloevich, Kutlumurotov Otabek Bekjanovich, Juraev Mirjalol Dehkonovich**
ABOUT THE PROBLEM OF BREAST CANCER RECURRENCE CAUSES.....323

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

48. **Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich, Gaibullaev Elbek Azizbekovich, Akramova Nozima Akramovna, Pustovetova Maria Genadievna**
ANALYSIS OF CYTOKINE PROFILE IN GINGIVAL CREVICULAR FLUID OF PATIENTS WITH AGGRESSIVE PERIODONTITIS: PATHOGENETIC AND DIAGNOSTIC ASPECTS.....333
49. **Daminova Nargiza Ravshanovna, Makhkamova Oqila Abdushukurovna, Sadikova Dilfuza Ravshanbekovna, Inogamov Sherzod Muhamatisakovich**
EVALUATION OF THE IMMUNOLOGICAL AND RESPIRATORY STATUS OF PATIENTS WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA WITH COMORBID PATHOLOGY OF THE ORAL CAVITY.....338
50. **Axmedov Xurshid Kamalovich**
ASSESSMENT OF STRUCTURAL AND FUNCTIONAL CHANGES IN PERIODONTAL TISSUES DURING PROSTHETICS WITH METAL-CERAMIC AND ZIRCONIUM DENTURES.....344
51. **Olimova Dildora Vohid qizi**
DENTAL DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH END-STAGE CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE (A STUDY OF PATIENTS RECEIVING AND NOT RECEIVING HEMODIALYSIS).352
52. **Zoyirov Tulkin Elnazarovich, Mardonova Dildora Kasimovna**
IMPROVEMENT OF TREATMENT METHODS FOR HYPERTROPHIC GINGIVITIS IN PATIENTS WITH EPILEPSY.....358

53. **Khotamova Madina Anvarovna, Odiljonova Mukhimaoy Savlatovna**
EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF PERIODONTITIS AND THE ORGANIZATION OF DENTAL MEASURES FOR WORKERS OF METAL PROCESSING ENTERPRISES.....366
54. **Umarova Makhfuza Usmanovna**
THE IMPACT OF CHRONIC USE OF NICOTINE-CONTAINING PRODUCTS ON THE PROGRESSION OF INFLAMMATORY-DYSTROPHIC DISEASES OF THE ORAL CAVITY: CLINICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS.....370
55. **Zoyirov Tulkin Elnazarovich, Allazarov Kuvondik Azadovich**
IMPROVING THE COMPLEX TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RECURRENT APHTHOUS STOMATITIS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC GASTRODUODENITIS.....377
56. **Allazarov Kuvondik Azadovich, Zoyirov Tulkin Elnazarovich.**
USE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF OZONE IN THE COMPLEX TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RECURRENT APHTHOUS STOMATITIS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC GASTRODUODENITIS385
57. **Mardonova Dildora Kasimovna, Zoyirov Tulkin Elnazarovich**
OPTIMIZATION OF METHODS FOR EXAMINING PERIODONT TISSUE DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH EPILEPSY393
58. **Akhmedov Ilhom Ibrohimovich, Kamalova Feruza Raxmatullaeva.**
CHANGES IN MICROFLORA NON-SPECIFIC FACTORS PROTECTION OF THE ORAL CAVITY IN CHILDREN WITH INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF MAXILLOFACIAL.....401
59. **Yuldashev Forrukh Farkhod Ugli, Kuryazov Akbar Kuranboevich, Khabibova Nazira Nasulloevna.**
EPIDEMIOLOGICAL FEATURES AND APPROACHES TO THE PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF DENTAL DISEASES IN DEAF-MUTE CHILDREN (REVIEW ARTICLE).....406
60. **Navruzova Ugilxon Orzijon Qizi, Xabibova Nazira Nasulloevna.**
THE ROLE OF IMMUNE STATUS IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF RECURRENT APHTHOUS STOMATITIS.....414
61. **Tojiyev Feruz Ibodulla ugli, Beysenbayev Nurbek Kunanbay ugli, Ismoilkhojaeva Komila G'ani qizi.**
RECONSTRUCTION OF MANDIBULAR DEFECTS IN CHILDREN WITH INDIVIDUALLY MANUFACTURED TITANIUM IMPLANTS AFTER REMOVAL OF BENIGN TUMORS.....419

FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION

62. **Giyasov Zaynitdin Asamutdinovich, Gulyamov Dilshod Erkinovich**
FORENSIC ASSESSMENT OF INJURIES TO MAJOR JOINTS IN ROAD TRAFFIC ACCIDENTS.....425

THERAPY AND INTERNAL MEDICINE

63. **Tashkenbayeva Eleonora Negmatovna, Esankulov Mukhammad Olimovich**
SIGNIFICANCE OF UROMODULIN IN THE DEVELOPMENT AND PROGRESSION OF CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE.....431

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

64. **Abrolov Hakimjon Kobiljonovich, Xolmurotov Akmal Abdumalikovich, Irisov Ortikali Tulaevich, Berdiev Kobiljon Bahromovich, Rakhimberganov Khusanboy Davlatnazarovich**
NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN DIAGNOSIS AND SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ASCENDING AORTIC ANEURYSM.....437

65. **Ashirov Mavlon Umirzakovitch.**
BIOMECHANICAL INSIGHTS INTO MDICO FOR FLATFOOT CORRECTION.....445
66. **Khodjanov Iskandar Yunusovich, Ubaydullaev Sherozbek Farkhodovich**
IMPROVING THE METHODS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF VALGOUS DEFORMATION OF THE ELBOW JOINT.....459
67. **Mamasoliev Bakhodir Mamausupovich**
FEATURES OF THROMBOEMBOLIC COMPLICATIONS PREVENTION DURING SURGICAL TREATMENT OF KNEE JOINT DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC LOWER LIMB VENOUS DISEASE.....468
68. **Melibayev Salimjon Tashtanovich, Karshiboyev Abduvakhob Jamboyevich, Nomazov Olim Ergash Og'Li, Jurayev Ilhom G'ulomovich**
VERTEBRAL COMPRESSION FRACTURES: CAUSES, DIAGNOSIS, AND MODERN TREATMENT STRATEGIES.....475
69. **Karshiboyev Abduvakhob Jamboyevich, Melibayev Salimjon Tashtanovich, Nomazov Olim Ergash Og'Li, Jalilov Khusan Mukhitdinovich.**
HIP FRACTURE, DIAGNOSIS, SURGICAL TREATMENT, REHABILITATION, THROMBOEMBOLIC PROPHYLAXIS, BISPHTHONATES, FALL PREVENTION.....489
70. **Kholkhudjayev Farrukh Ikramovich**
RESULTS OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ROTATOR CUFF INJURIES OF THE SHOULDER JOINT.....502
71. **Tilyakov Xasan Azizovich, Temurov Alisher Akmaljon O'g'li, Xursanov Muxriddin Xusniddin O'g'li, Yusupov Sohijon Saitxon O'g'li, Tolmasov Mirjalol Mirzohid O'g'li.**
RESULTS OF THE APPLICATION OF ADVANCED OSTEOSYNTHESIS IN DIAPHYSEAL FRACTURES OF THE HUMERUS.....508

RADIATION IMAGING

72. **Ikramova Zulfiya Tulkinovna, Rozikhodjaeva Gulnora Ahmedovna, Soipova Guzal Gulomidinovna**
ASSESSMENT OF TOTAL CEREBRAL BLOOD FLOW IN PATIENTS WITH CAROTIC ATHEROSCLEROSIS.....515

SURGERY

73. **Akhmedov Adkham Ibadullaevich, Fayazov Abdulaziz Djalilovich**
PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF MOTOR-EVACUATION DYSFUNCTION OF THE GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT IN SEVERELY BURNED PATIENTS.....523
74. **Sayinaev Farrukh Karamatovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich**
LAPAROSCOPIC AND OPEN HERNIOPLASTY FOR VENTRAL HERNIAS: SURGICAL OUTCOMES AND COMPLICATIONS ASSESSMENT.....532
75. **Daminov Feruz Asatullaevich, Shomurodov Khabibullo Abdumalik Ugli, Rakhmonov Kosim Erdanovich.**
OPTIMIZATION OF SURGICAL TACTICS IN ACUTE DESTRUCTIVE CHOLECYSTITIS: THE ROLE OF LAPAROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY AND RISK FACTOR ANALYSIS.....539
76. **Khayitov Laziz Milionerovich, Khakimov Erkin Abdikhalilovich, Zuvaytov Shoxrux G'ayrat o'g'li, Abrorov Shahbozjon Nematzoda**
THE ROLE ENDOBRONCHIAL COMPLEX THERAPY AT PATIENTS WITH THE INHALATION TRAUMA.....544

OPHTHALMOLOGY

77. **Fayzieva Dilorom Buritoshevna, Akhmedova Dilafruz Baxadirovna, Mirzaev Dilshodbek Akhmedovich.**
VISUAL DISORDERS AND THEIR IMPACT ON PERIPHERAL VISION AND EYE MOVEMENT COORDINATION.....549

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ
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ERGAShEVA Munisa Yakubovna
PhD
Samarkand State Medical University**IMPROVING MEASURES FOR REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN WITH
DISABILITIES DUE TO NERVOUS SYSTEM DISEASES**

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 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15008232>**ABSTRACT**

In order to improve rehabilitation measures for disabled children due to diseases of the nervous system and to evaluate its effectiveness, 865 children under 18 years of age who are disabled due to cerebral palsy (CP), diseases of the peripheral nervous system, and meningoencephalitis were selected. In the first group, 78% of children had cerebral palsy, 13.4% had diseases of the peripheral nervous system, and 8.6% had meningoencephalitis. In the second control group, 76.8% of children had cerebral palsy, 14.4% had diseases of the peripheral nervous system, and 8.8% had meningoencephalitis. The study used examination methods based on the adaptation of children to social life. Children with disabilities due to CP were assessed based on characteristics that limit their life activities. The effectiveness of complex rehabilitation of children with disabilities due to spastic diplegia of cerebral palsy was also determined. It was noted that the percentage of disabled children due to cerebral palsy decreased.

Key words: rehabilitation, cerebral palsy, disabled person, goniometry.

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**ASAB TIZIMI KASALLIKLARI YUZASIDAN NOGIRONLIGI BO'LGAN BOLALARDA
REABILITATSIYA CHORA-TADBIRLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH****ANNOTATSIYA**

Tadqiqotda asab tizimi kasalliklari yuzasidan nogironligi bo'lgan bolalarda reabilitatsiya chora-tadbirlarini takomillashtirish va uning samaradorligini baholash uchun bolalar bosh miya falaji (BBMF), periferik asab tizimi kasalliklari va meningoensefalit natijasida nogiron bo'lgan 865 nafar 18 yoshgacha bo'lgan bolalarni tanlab olingan. I-asosiy guruhda 78% bolalarda bolalar bosh miya falaji, 13,4% da periferik asab tizimi kasalliklari va 8,6% da meningoensefalit nogironlikka olib

kelganligi aniqlangan. II-nazorat guruhida esa 76,8% bolalarda bolalar bosh miya falaji, 14,4% da periferik asab tizimi kasalliklari va 8,8% da meningoensefalit nogironlikka olib kelgan. Tadqiqot davomida bolalarni ijtimoiy hayotga moslashishi jihatidan kelib chiqqan holda tekshiruv usullari o'tkazilgan. Bunda bolalar bosh miya falaji tufayli nogironligi bo'lgan bolalar hayot faoliyatini cheklovchi xususiyatlariga ko'ra baholandi. Shuningdek, BBMF spastik diplegiya turi yuzasidan nogironligi bo'lgan bolalarda kompleks reabilitatsiya samaradorligi aniqlandi. Bunda bolalar bosh miya falaji tufayli nogironligi bo'lgan bolalar hayot faoliyatini cheklovchi xususiyatlarining darajalariga ega bolalar ulushi kamayishi qayd etildi.

Kalit so'zlar: reabilitatsiya, bolalar bosh miya falaji, nogiron, goniometriya.

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СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕРОПРИЯТИЙ ПО РЕАБИЛИТАЦИИ ДЕТЕЙ С ИНВАЛИДНОСТЬЮ ВСЛЕДСТВИЕ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ НЕРВНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

С целью совершенствования реабилитационных мероприятий детей-инвалидов вследствие заболеваний нервной системы и оценки ее эффективности было отобрано 865 детей в возрасте до 18 лет, являющихся инвалидами вследствие детского церебрального паралича (ДЦП), заболеваний периферической нервной системы и менингоэнцефалита. В первой группе у 78% детей был детский церебральный паралич, у 13,4% - заболевания периферической нервной системы, у 8,6% - менингоэнцефалит.

Во II контрольной группе у 76,8% детей был детский церебральный паралич, у 14,4% - заболевания периферической нервной системы, у 8,8% - менингоэнцефалит. В ходе исследования были проведены методы обследования, основанные на адаптации детей к социальной жизни. Дети с ограниченными возможностями вследствие ДЦП оценивались по характеристикам, ограничивающим их жизнедеятельность. Также определена эффективность комплексной реабилитации детей с ограниченными возможностями здоровья вследствие спастической диплегии ДЦП. Было отмечено, что снизился процент детей-инвалидов по причине ДЦП.

Ключевые слова: реабилитация, детский церебральный паралич, инвалид, гониометрия.

Kirish. Reabilitatsiya – bu organizm funktsiyalarining doimiy buzilishi bilan bog'liq muammolar natijasida yuzaga keladigan hayot cheklovlarini bartaraf etishga yoki to'liqroq qoplashga qaratilgan tibbiy, psixologik, pedagogik, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy chora-tadbirlar jarayoni va tizimi. Reabilitatsiyaning asosiy maqsadi - ilgari yo'qolgan funktsiyalarni tiklash. Hozirgi vaqtda butun dunyoda reabilitatsiya usullari keng rivojlanmoqda. Turli kasalliklarni davolash va alohida organlarning faoliyatini tiklash bemorga - jamiyatda, oilada va mehnat jamoasida ma'lum o'rin egallagan individual xususiyatlarga ega bo'lgan shaxsga ta'sir qilishning murakkab tizimining bir qismidir.

Hozirgi vaqtda ota-onalarning bolalardagi kasallik belgilaridan yetarlicha xabardor bo'lmaganligi sababli mutaxassislariga murojaat qilishda kechikish kuzatilmoqda, xususan, markaziy asab tizimi, ayniqsa, tug'ilgandan 1 yoshgacha bo'lgan bolalarda. Bu holat kasallikning rivojlanishiga va davolanish va tibbiy reabilitatsiyaning kech boshlanishiga olib keladi. Mavjud vaziyat kasalliklarning tibbiy profilaktikasiga qaratilgan kompleks chora-tadbirlarni amalga oshirishni taqozo etmoqda.

Markaziy asab tizimining patologiyasi bo'lgan bolalarni kompleks reabilitatsiya qilish tizimi Respublikaning davlat organlari, mahalliy hokimiyat organlari, ish beruvchilar, notijorat tashkilotlari, shu jumladan jamoat birlashmalari, kasaba uyushmalari, ommaviy axborot vositalari, fuqarolar ishtirokida ko'p predmetli faoliyat sifatida shakllantiriladi va amalga oshiriladi. Integratsiyalashgan

yondashuv va zamonaviy usullarning kombinatsiyasi hozirgi vaqtda turli xil nevrologik kasalliklarga chalingan bolalar va o'smirlarning buzilishlarini korreksiyalashda eng yaxshi natijalarga erishishga imkon beradi.

Maqsad: asab tizimi kasalliklari yuzasidan nogironligi bo'lgan bolalarda reabilitatsiya chora-tadbirlarini takomillashtirish va uning samaradorligini baholash.

Tadqiqot materiali va usullari. Biz asab tizimi kasalliklari yuzasidan nogironligi bo'lgan bolalarda reabilitatsiya chora-tadbirlarini takomillashtirish va uning samaradorligini baholash uchun tadqiqot obyekti sifatida bolalar bosh miya falaji, tutqanoq va tutqanoq holati, periferik asab tizimi kasalliklari va bosh miyada o'tkir qon aylanishi buzilishi natijasida nogiron bo'lgan Samarqand viloyatidan 865 nafar 18 yoshgacha bo'lgan bolalarni tanlab oldik.

Tadqiqot natijalari. Tadqiqotga kiritilgan nogironligi bo'lgan bolalar yoshiga ko'ra 4 ta yosh guruhlariga bo'lib tahlil qilindi. Jumladan, I-asosiy guruhda 1 yoshgacha bo'lgan bolalar – 86 (19,4%) nafarni, 1-3 yoshli bolalar – 91 (20,6%) nafarni, 4-6 yoshli bolalar – 125 (28,3%) nafarni va 7-18 yoshli bolalar – 140 (31,7%) nafarni tashkil qildi. II-nazorat guruhida esa 1 yoshgacha bo'lgan bolalar – 63 (14,9%) nafarni, 1-3 yoshli bolalar – 102 (24,1%) nafarni, 4-6 yoshli bolalar – 135 (32%) nafarni va 7-18 yoshli bolalar – 123 (29%) nafarni tashkil qildi. Nogironligi bo'lgan bolalarning jinsiga ko'ra tahlilida I-asosiy guruhda bolalarning 51,6% ni o'g'il bolalar va 48,4% ni qiz bolalar tashkil qilishdi. II-nazorat guruhida esa 51,3% ni o'g'il bolalar va 48,7% ni qiz bolalar tashkil qilishdi. Yuqoridagidan ko'rinib turibdiki tadqiqot guruhleri o'rtasida bolalar yoshi va jinsiga ko'ra sezilarli farqlar aniqlanmadi va taqqoslash uchun maqbul guruhlar hisoblanadi.

Samarqand viloyatida bolalarda nogironlikka olib kelgan asab tizimi kasalliklari turlari bo'yicha o'tkazilgan tahlil natijalariga ko'ra, aksariyat bolalarda nogironlikka bolalar bosh miya falaji, tutqanoq va tutqanoq holati, periferik asab tizimi kasalliklari va bosh miyada o'tkir qon aylanishi buzilishi sabab bo'lganligi aniqlandi. Shu munosabat bilan biz asab tizimi kasalliklari yuzasidan nogironligi bo'lgan bolalarda reabilitatsiya chora-tadbirlarini takomillashtirish va uning samaradorligini baholash uchun tadqiqot obyekti sifatida bolalar bosh miya falaji (BBMF), periferik asab tizimi kasalliklari va meningoensefalit natijasida nogiron bo'lgan 865 nafar 18 yoshgacha bo'lgan bolalarni tanlab oldik. I-asosiy guruhda 78% bolalarda bolalar bosh miya falaji, 13,4% da periferik asab tizimi kasalliklari va 8,6% da meningoensefalit nogironlikka olib kelganligi aniqlandi. II-nazorat guruhida esa 76,8% bolalarda bolalar bosh miya falaji, 14,4% da periferik asab tizimi kasalliklari va 8,8% da meningoensefalit nogironlikka olib kelgan. Biz tadqiqot davomida bolalarni ijtimoiy hayotga moslashishi jihatidan kelib chiqqan holda tekshiruv usullarini o'tkazdik. Bunda bolalar bosh miya falaji tufayli nogironligi bo'lgan bolalar hayot faoliyatini cheklovchi xususiyatlariga ko'ra baholandi. BBMF klinik shakllariga ko'ra quyidagi turlari farqlandi. BBMF bilan tekshirilgan I-asosiy guruhdagi va II-nazorat guruhidagi bolalarning 13,7% da (mos ravishda 12,4 va 15,1%) gemiparetik shakli, 14,3% da (mos ravishda 15,6% va 13%) giperkinetik shakli, 9,4% da (mos ravishda 11,1% va 7,6%) ikki tomonlama gemiplegiya, 16,4% da (mos ravishda 15,1% va 17,8%) atonik-astatik shakli, 46,1% da (mos ravishda 45,8% va 46,5%) spastik diplegiya aniqlandi. Biz ishlab chiqilgan reabilitatsiya chora-tadbirlari samaradorligini baholash uchun bolalar miya falajining spastik diplegiya turi tufayli nogironligi bo'lgan bolalarni tanlab oldik.

BBMF spastik diplegiya turi yuzasidan nogironligi bo'lgan bolalarning hayot faoliyatini yetakchi chekloviga ko'ra tahlil qildik. Bolalar bosh miya falajining spastik diplegiya turi yuzasidan nogironligi bo'lgan asosiy va nazorat guruhi bolalarining hayot faoliyatini cheklovchi yetakchi nuqsonlar II va III darajali o'z-o'ziga xizmat qilish, harakatlanish, oriyentatsiya va muloqotning buzilishi bo'ldi (mos ravishda asosiy guruhda 87,4%, 75,3%, 80,4%, 80,4%; nazorat guruhida 80,8%, 73,5%, 80,2%, 71,5%).

Biz asosiy guruhga kiritilgan BBMF spastik diplegiya turi yuzasidan nogironligi bo'lgan bolalarda kompleks reabilitatsiya chora-tadbirlarini o'tkazdik. Bolalarga pediatr, nevropatolog va boshqa tor mutaxassislar tomonidan ko'rikdan so'ng BBMF spastik diplegiya tashxisi asosida nogironlik belgilangach, har 6 oyda davlat va nodavlat reabilitatsiya muassasalarida 20 kunlik statsionar davolashdan o'tishdi va ota-onalariga uy sharoitida bajarishlari kerak bo'lgan jismoniy mashqlar majmui o'rgatildi. Kompleks reabilitatsiya chora-tadbirlarini tarkibida qo'l-oyoqlarga

parafin-ozokeritli applikatsiyalar, 45-48°C haroratda, 15-20 daqiqa, 10 ta muolaja, har kuni qo'llanildi; 10 kun davomida mushaklarning tonusini, qon va limfa oqimini normallashtirish, kontrakturalarning rivojlanishiga yo'l qo'ymaslik va to'qimalarning metabolizmini kuchaytirish uchun umumiy massaj o'tkazildi; mushaklar kuchini oshirish maqsadida har kuni 20 daqiqa davomida davolovchi jismoniy mashqlar hamda tayanch-harakat a'zolarining reaksiyasini yaxshilovchi suzish mashqi 15 daqiqadan kun ora 10 ta kurs bilan o'tkazildi; har kuni 20 kun davomida 20 daqiqadan manual mushaklarni cho'zish mashqlari o'tkazildi; shuningdek, Gross stimulyatorida 20 daqiqalik mashqlar davomida bolalarga yordamsiz harakatlanish, o'z o'qi atrofida aylanish, velosipedda mashq qilish o'rgatildi; Koreyaning FORTIS brendining ippoterapiya simulyatorida 20 daqiqalik mashqlar BBMF bo'lgan bolalarda harakatlarni muvofiqlashtirishni yaxshiladi va psixo-emotsional sohaning rivojlanishiga hissa qo'shdi.

Bolalar bosh miya falaji yuzasidan nogironligi bolalarda kompleks reabilitatsiya chora-tadbirlari algoritmi

BBMF spastik diplegiya turi yuzasidan nogironligi bo'lgan bolalarda kompleks reabilitatsiya chora-tadbirlarini o'tkazishning asosiy shartlari shundaki, o'tkazilayotgan muolajalar bolada mavjud anormalliklarga va yoshiga mos kelishi kerak, barcha manipulyatsiyalar og'riqsiz amalga oshirilishi, bolaga yangi trenajerlar bilan shig'ullanishdan oldin uni tanishtirish va vizual-manual kontakti ta'minlash kerak, muolajalar bajarilayotganida bola oldida onalari ham bo'lishi bir tomondan ularni tinchlantirsa, ikkinchi tomondan onalariga muolajalarni o'rgatishga imkon beradi.

Biz tadqiqot davomida bolalarni ijtimoiy hayotga moslashishi jihatidan kelib reabilitatsiya samaradorligini baholadik. Bunda bolalar bosh miya falaji tufayli nogironligi bo'lgan bolalar hayot faoliyatini cheklovchi xususiyatlarining darajalariga ega bolalar ulushi kamayishi qayd etildi. I-asosiy guruh bolalarining barchasida ijobiy dinamika kuzatildi. I-asosiy guruh bolalarida III darajali hayot faoliyatini cheklanishi muloqotga kirishish (5,3 marta), harakatlanish va oriyentatsiyada (2,4 marta), o'ynash faoliyatida (3,7 marta), o'z hulqini nazorat qilish mezonlarida (2,1 marta) sezilarli kamaydi. O'z-o'ziga xizmat qilishda ham ijobiy dinamika kuzatildi (2,1 marta). Shuningdek, birinchi darajali hayot faoliyati cheklovi bo'lgan bolalar sonining oshganligi qayd etildi, jumladan, o'z-o'ziga xizmat qilish, harakatlanish va o'ynash faoliyatida (mos ravishda 4,1, 1,8 va 1,7 marta), nisbatan kamroq o'zgarish o'z hulqini nazorat qilish, oriyentatsiya va muloqotga kirishish mezonlarida kuzatildi (mos ravishda 1,6, 1,5 va 1,1 marta). II-nazorat guruhi bolalarida III darajali hayot faoliyatini cheklanishi muloqotga kirishish (3,8 marta), o'z hulqini nazorat qilish mezonlarida (2,3 marta), harakatlanish (2,1 marta) va oriyentatsiyada (1,6 marta), o'ynash faoliyatida (1,5 marta) sezilarli kamaydi. Birinchi darajali hayot faoliyati cheklovi bo'lgan bolalar sonining oshganligi o'z-o'ziga xizmat qilish (2,5 marta), oriyentatsiya mezonlarida kuzatildi (1,3 marta), nisbatan kamroq o'zgarish o'z hulqini nazorat qilish, va muloqotga kirishish (mos ravishda 1,13 va 1,26 marta), harakatlanish va o'ynash faoliyati (mos ravishda 1,02 va 1,06 marta) mezonlarida kuzatildi.

BBMF spastik diplegiya turi yuzasidan nogironligi bo'lgan bolalarning vestibulyar funksiyasi va tovonning tayanch xususiyati muvozanatni ushlab turish muddatiga ko'ra kompleks davolashda har kuni dinamikada qayd qilib borildi. Ushbu test natijalari baholanganda asosiy guruh bemorlarida muvozanatni ushlab turish muddati $32,4 \pm 2,8$ sekunddan $122,8 \pm 7,4$ sekundgacha oshdi ($p < 0,05$). II-nazorat guruhidagi bolalarda ham muvozanatga funksional testning ijobiy dinamikasi kuzatildi. Muvozanatni ushlab turish muddati $30,8 \pm 3,2$ sekunddan $98,6 \pm 6,8$ sekundgacha oshdi ($p < 0,05$). Vaqt intervali baholanishiga ko'ra oxirgi mashg'ulot ko'rsatkichi asosiy guruhda nazorat guruhiga qaraganda 24,5% ishonchli yuqoriligi aniqlandi.

O'tkazilayotgan reabilitatsiya chora-tadbirlarining samaradorligini baholashda bolalarning harakat faoliyatini baholash muhim o'rin tutadi. BBMF spastik diplegiya turida bolalarning qadami tovonning ekvino-varus holati tufayli qisqargan bo'ladi, shuningdek, tananing chayqalishi, tebranishi, qo'llarning birgalikdagi harakati yo'qligi tufayli harakat koordinatsiyasi buzilishi kuzatildi. Bolalarning harakat faolligi qadam uzunligi, 1 daqiqada yurish tezligi va o'tirib-turish soniga ko'ra baholandi. Reabilitatsiyagacha BBMF bo'lgan bolalarning o'rtacha qadam uzunligi $14,9 \pm 0,3$ sm ni

tashkil qildi. Asosiy guruhda reabilitatsiya kursidan so'ng $20,8 \pm 0,4$ sm, nazorat guruhida $18,6 \pm 0,3$ sm qayd qilindi.

Reabilitatsiyagacha 1 daqiqada qadam soni I-asosiy guruhdagi bolalarda $29,3 \pm 0,4$ tani, II-nazorat guruhida $28,3 \pm 0,3$ tani tashkil qildi. Reabilitatsiya kursidan so'ng asosiy guruhda 1 daqiqada qadamlar soni 9 taga oshganligi ($p < 0,05$), nazorat guruhida esa 2 taga oshganligi qayd qilindi. Asosiy guruh bolalarida qadam uzunligi va tezligining oshishi hisobiga diskoordinatsiya belgilar ham kamaydi. BMMF bo'lgan bolalarda yurish tekisroq va tana tebranishi kamaydi. 1 daqiqada o'tirib-turish soni BMMF spastik diplegiya turiga chalingan asosiy guruh bolalarida $6,7 \pm 0,3$ tadan $8,4 \pm 0,3$ taga ($p < 0,05$), nazorat guruhida esa $7,2 \pm 0,3$ tadan $8,2 \pm 0,3$ taga oshdi.

Shuningdek, reabilitatsion chora-tadbirlarning samaradorligini BMMF spastik diplegiya turi yuzasidan nogironligi bo'lgan bolalarda qo'l-oyoqlarda goniometriya o'lchamlari ham ko'rsatdi. Jumladan, I-asosiy guruh bolalarida o'ng qo'l bilak-kaft bo'g'imida bukish 10° ga, yozish 6° ga, chap qo'l bilak-kaft bo'g'imida bukish 15° ga, yozish 7° ga oshdi, II-nazorat guruhida esa o'ng qo'l bilak-kaft bo'g'imida mos ravishda 6° va 3° ga, chap qo'l bilak-kaft bo'g'imida 8° va 5° ga oshdi. Tirsak bo'g'imida bukish tekshirilganda I-asosiy guruh bolalarida o'ng qo'l 13° ga va chap qo'l 14° ga oshdi, II-nazorat guruhida esa o'ng qo'l 6° ga va chap qo'l 8° ga oshdi.

Oyoqlarda chanoq-son bo'g'imidagi va tizza bo'g'imidagi harakatlar cheklanishidagi o'zgarishlar ham goniometriya ko'rsatkichlarida ijobiy dinamika kuzatildi. Jumladan, I-asosiy guruh bolalarida o'ng oyoq bukilganda chanoq-son bo'g'imida bukish 22° ga va o'ng oyoq tik holatida chanoq-son bo'g'imida bukish 11° ga oshdi ($p < 0,05$), chap oyoq bukilganda chanoq-son bo'g'imida bukish 24° ga va chap oyoq tik holatida chanoq-son bo'g'imida bukish 12° ga oshdi ($p < 0,05$). II-nazorat guruhi bolalarida esa o'ng oyoq bukilganda chanoq-son bo'g'imida bukish 9° ga va o'ng oyoq tik holatida chanoq-son bo'g'imida bukish 3° ga oshdi ($p < 0,05$), chap oyoq bukilganda chanoq-son bo'g'imida bukish 10° ga va chap oyoq tik holatida chanoq-son bo'g'imida bukish 3° ga oshdi.

Shuningdek, tizza bo'g'imi va boldir-tovon bo'g'imi goniometriyasida bukish gradusida ijobiy dinamika kuzatildi. I-asosiy guruh bolalarida tizza bo'g'imida bukish o'ng oyoqda 24o ga, chap oyoqda 16o ga oshdi ($p < 0,05$), boldir-tovon bo'g'imida esa bukish o'ng oyoqda 24o ga, chap oyoqda 25o ga kamaydi ($p < 0,05$). II-nazorat guruhi bolalarida esa tizza bo'g'imida bukish o'ng oyoqda 10o ga, chap oyoqda 11o ga oshdi ($p < 0,05$), boldir-tovon bo'g'imida esa bukish o'ng oyoqda 8o ga, chap oyoqda 6o ga kamaydi.

BMMF spastik diplegiya turi yuzasidan nogironligi bo'lgan bolalarning barchasida goniometriyada qo'l-oyoq bo'g'imlariga harakat cheklanishida har ikkala guruhda ijobiy dinamika aniqlandi. II-nazorat guruhiga qaraganda I-asosiy guruhning goniometriya ko'rsatkichlari dinamikasida me'yoriy ko'rsatkichlarga 86,4% yaqinlashganligi aniqlandi. Bu o'tkazilgan reabilitatsiya chora-tadbirlari bolalarda spastik holatni kamaytirganligini ko'rsatdi.

Spazm darajasini baholash uchun modifikatsiyalangan Eshvort shkalasi (Modified Ashworth Scale for Grading Spasticity) qo'llanildi. Shkala ko'rsatkichlariga ko'ra asosiy va nazorat guruhidagi bolalarda reabilitatsiya chora-tadbirlaridan so'ng I-asosiy guruhda 3,2% bolalarda oyoq-qo'lning passiv bukish yoki yozish paytida yoki bo'g'imdagi harakat oralig'i oxirida normal tonusga qaytish bilan "ushlab olish" ni keltirib chiqaradigan mushak tonusining biroz oshishiga erishildi. 14,5% bolalarda mushak tonusining biroz oshishi, 53,2% bolalarda passiv harakatlar saqlangan holda mushak tonusining sezilarli darajada oshishi, 26,5% bolalarda passiv harakatlar qiyinlashgan holda mushak tonusining sezilarli darajada oshishi va 2,5% bolalarda passiv harakatsiz oyoq-qo'lning qattiq bukilgan yoki yozilgan holati qayd etildi. II-nazorat guruhida esa spazm darajasini baholashda 12% bolalarda mushak tonusining biroz oshishi, 46,4% bolalarda passiv harakatlar saqlangan holda mushak tonusining sezilarli darajada oshishi, 31,1% bolalarda passiv harakatlar qiyinlashgan holda mushak tonusining sezilarli darajada oshishi va 10,5% bolalarda passiv harakatsiz oyoq-qo'lning qattiq bukilgan yoki yozilgan holati qayd etildi. I-asosiy guruh bolalarida II-guruh bolalariga qaraganda reabilitatsiya chora-tadbirlaridan so'ng qo'l-oyoqlarda spazm darajasi pasayishi 85,7% ga yaxshilandi ($p < 0,05$).

Xulosa. Shunday qilib, nogironlarni, shu jumladan, nogiron bolalarni asab tizimi patologiyasi tufayli reabilitatsiya qilish nogironlarni jamiyat hayotida ishtirok etishlari uchun teng imkoniyatlar yaratishga qaratilgan sharoitlar bilan ta'minlash tizimining muhim elementidir.

Tadqiqotimizda o'tkazilgan reabilitatsiya chora-tadbirlaridan so'ng bolalar bosh miya falaji tufayli nogirirligi bo'lgan bolalar hayot faoliyatini cheklovchi xususiyatlarining darajalariga ega bolalar ulushi kamayishi qayd etildi. Bunda I-asosiy guruhda II-guruh bolalariga qaraganda qo'l-oyoqlarda spazm darajasi pasayishi 85,7% ga yaxshilandi. Muvozanatni ushlab turish muddati $30,8 \pm 3,2$ sekunddan $98,6 \pm 6,8$ sekundgacha oshdi. Reabilitatsiya kursidan so'ng asosiy guruhda 1 daqiqada qadamlar soni 9 taga oshganligi, nazorat guruhida esa 2 taga oshganligi qayd qilindi. Vaqt intervali baholanishiga ko'ra oxirgi mashg'ulot ko'rsatkichi asosiy guruhda nazorat guruhiga qaraganda 24,5% ishonchli yuqoriligi aniqlandi.

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